

Leveraging Graph Analytics for Energy Efficiency Certificates

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Abstract: As energy efficiency is becoming a subject of utter importance in today's societies, the European Union and a vast number of organizations have put a lot of focus on it. As a result, huge amounts of data are generated at an unprecedented rate. After thorough analysis and exploration, these data could provide a variety of solutions and optimizations regarding the energy efficiency subject. However, all the potential solutions that could derive from the aforementioned procedures still remain untapped due to the fact that these data are yet fragmented and highly sophisticated. In this paper, we propose an architecture for a Reasoning Engine, a mechanism that provides intelligent querying, insights and search capabilities, by leveraging technologies that will be described below. The proposed architecture has been developed in the context of the H2020 project called MATRYCS. In this paper, the reasons that resulted from the need of efficient ways of querying and analyzing the large amounts of data are firstly explained. Subsequently, several use cases, where related technologies were used to address real-world challenges, are presented. The main focus, however, is put in the detailed presentation of our Reasoning Engine's implementation steps. Lastly, the outcome of our work is demonstrated, showcasing the derived results and the optimizations that have been implemented.

Citation: Kapsalis, P.; Kormpakis, G.; Alexakis, K.; Askounis, D.

Leveraging Graph Analytics for Energy Efficiency Certificates.

Energies **2022**, *15*, 1500.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/en15041500>

Academic Editor: Adrián

Mota Babiloni

Received: 27 December 2021

Accepted: 15 February 2022

Published: 17 February 2022

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

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Keywords: energy efficiency; semantics; reasoning engine; digital twin; big graph analytics; knowledge bases; data processing semantic enrichment

1. Introduction

Energy efficiency is among the top priorities of the European Union, and for that reason, a European framework [1] as well as a number of directives [2,3] have been established. These initiatives generate a vast amount of diverse data, which are yet fragmented, and, as a result, they cannot be utilized for data analysis, intelligent querying, and extraction of patterns. Thus, the need of graph analytics arises, aiming for the extraction and visualization of these data, as well as the creation of knowledge databases that will contain information about energy performance analytics and the related buildings. Moreover, by enabling graph solutions and the available knowledge from digital twins [4], the added value of these data can be enhanced, since, additionally to their usage as individual data points, the interconnections between them are also explored. Moreover, the installation of more and more sensors and IoT-based systems [5,6] has led to an enormous volume of generated data. The analysis and process of these data can be beneficial in the monitoring [7] and management of energy consumption [8–11], as well as in the decision-making process regarding energy consumption [12,13].

The efficient management of energy consumption and generation is more than necessary due to the increasing CO₂ emissions from the building stock and the threats of climate change. The buildings have turned to solutions that include the adoption of more and more sensors (IoT), as well as information and communication technologies (ICT), feeding more and more of the generated data to artificial intelligence (AI) models [14] that need to process

them. The handling of these data can play a crucial role in the mitigation of CO₂ emissions and in the establishment of more efficient energy management.

The combination of the aforementioned technologies and the exploitation of big data [15] can lead to a decarbonized future with significantly less CO₂ emissions from building operations. Following this approach, it is necessary to understand how the existing technologies, methods, as well as models and solutions, could be integrated by the building sector. This approach is vital in order to generate knowledge from the building data and constitutes the Big Data Value Chain (BDVC), which plays a key role in the energy economy of the future, providing more opportunities towards the vision of further digitalization and, thus, accelerating the energy transition.

The Reasoning Engine is the component responsible for the handling of the metadata produced by the buildings, and it does so by leveraging the graph analytic capabilities. To be more specific, the Reasoning Engine is a mechanism that provides intelligent querying, insights, and search capabilities by leveraging the available knowledge for the digital twin and analytics services. It also provides functionalities for the addition of more data to the existing knowledge base. The Reasoning Engine module is capable of consuming data produced from various sources (e.g., REST APIs, databases, files, etc.) and of both JSON and RDF formats. After being received, these data are persisted to the Reasoning Engine's graph database, which (Neo4j [16]) is a powerful inference engine that enables graph functionalities over entities and connections for extracting new insights and patterns from datasets.

Graph databases are one of the latest strategies in big data storage for buildings that arise in popularity thanks to their ever-increasing accessibility. Graph databases are constructed to handle highly connected and linked data effectively. Therefore, they are a very promising approach for inference analysis. Multiple benchmarks highlight their strengths, comparing them to their non-graph database variant when applied to highly connected data [17]. This is implied by expensive JOIN operations in non-graph databases, while graph databases offer to traverse a large number of connections in a very short amount of time.

In the context of the H2020 project MATRYCS (<https://matrycs.eu> accessed date 28 December 2021), a reasoning engine was implemented using the data from EREN pilot. The aforementioned data are energy performance certificates from buildings in Castilla y León and contain information about the buildings' location (coordinates, municipality, province), primary energy consumption, energy ratings, CO₂ emissions, heating and cooling demands, registration date, and number. In this paper, we contribute to the Reasoning Engine functionality by enabling graph functionalities and properties over linked data instead of web ontologies and RDF schemas, aiming to extract added value from linked and connected data. Neo4j is a well-known graph database with an attached query language, CYPHER (<https://neo4j.com/developer/cypher/> accessed date 28 December 2021). While a graph is not an ontology, an ontology can be represented in a graph. The challenge of this work is to use CYPHER to query not just a graph but also a knowledge graph. We will describe the work carried out in order to enable Neo4j to use JSON and RDF data as input and translate queries from SPARQL (<https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/> accessed date 28 December 2021), which is the query language of ontologies, to CYPHER. Additionally, we aim to use Neo4j to store ontologies and JSON data in both streaming and batch format. The aim of generating semantic information through graph database functionalities is to optimise the AI models' data-driven energy predictions in urban infrastructure.

A reasoning engine for the building sector, and more specifically for energy efficiency certificates, is of significant importance for the improvement actions and pattern recognition by leveraging axioms and rules over the input data. In the present use case, the input data are the EREN energy certificates. The pattern recognition pipeline is based on logical inferences that evaluate the input data using graph properties and entities. The result of this procedure is the enhancement of the input for prediction models applied in the building sector, which process a large volume and variety of both real-time and historical data, in order to extract meaningful information and make data driven decisions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 analyzes the state of the art of the treated domain. In Section 3, the architecture and the implementation of the Reasoning Engine, and the way the different sub-components are organized around a graph database, are described. Section 4 presents the results from queries to Reasoning Engine REST APIs, and Section 5 summarizes the key issues that have arisen in this paper.

2. State of the Art Analysis

NoSQL databases are non-tabular databases. They store data differently than relational tables, and they are categorized depending on the way they store the data [18]. Over time, four major types of NoSQL databases have emerged: document databases, key-value databases, wide-column stores, and graph databases [19]. The majority of reasoning engines utilize NoSQL databases and more specifically graph databases. This kind of database has built-in inference engines to manage the stored data. For this development, and considering the graph database utilization, Neo4j (<https://neo4j.com/> accessed date 29 December 2021) [20] is broadly used in reasoning engine use cases. Graph databases have features including reliability, high availability, fast response, and a high level of replication [21]. These characteristics make this kind of database widely used in various sectors such as banking, networking, and aviation. The main advantage of using a graph database is the relationship established between the element and the power of inference that this structure provides. Therefore, they are mainly used in fraud detection, graph-based search, intelligent querying, and real time traffic managements and recommendations.

One of the use-cases where the Neo4j graph database was used is the case of the “Panama Papers”, where the International Consortium of Investigative Journalists utilized Neo4j to store and process information provided by the whole journalist network [22].

Another real-world use case where a graph database was used is the one related to the multinational retail corporation, Walmart, which used it for the improvement of the customer experience in its stores. More specifically, Neo4j data science algorithms were leveraged to measure centrality, betweenness, and similarity. This resulted in the replacement of the old, low-latency legacy systems by Neo4j that provided recommendations and inference by combining historical and user session data [23].

Moreover, NBC News once made usage of Neo4j for the analysis of a vast number of tweets made by Russian agents during the 2016 U.S. Presidential election. What NBC was aiming to showcase was how Twitter was used as a communication channel to spread disinformation and stimulate division [24].

The presented use cases showcase how graph databases’ features, such as performance, flexibility, network management, and social interconnect, are used in real life applications to enhance their efficiency and to extract insights from data.

Cloud-computing applications that leverage graph databases currently produce large-scale big graphs and reasoning applications in order to extract interesting, meaningful, and exploitable insights and patterns from these data. As a result, analytics over graphs is now a top-tier challenge in database and reasoning research, and this has resulted in a fast-growing interest of this field from both the academical and the industrial community.

The big graph analytics problem arises in several application scenarios that belong to a wide range of fields. Following, an example of end-to-end processing and an example of graph time times are demonstrated.

The work of [25] focused on a framework that supports end-to-end graph processing, achieved by proceeding to complex neighborhood-centric analysis over big graphs in Cloud environments. This method is called NSCALE. NSCALE introduces an abstraction that not only allows reasoning on graph analytics via sub-graphs, but also supports two metrics of utter importance: performance and memory optimization.

The work of [26] provides architecture and main functionalities of a tool known as VERTEXICA. VERTEXICA supports big graph analytics, and the main benefit it provides is that it works on top of relational DBMS. Using VERTEXICA, the end-users can avoid the restrictions that arise from the usage of plain SQL statements. Instead, they are able to

exploit natural vertex-centric interfaces for defining analytics over big graphs, where all the data management activities, including query processing, can be expressed via an intuitive graphical interface.

3. Methodology, Architecture, and Implementation

3.1. Methodology

The methodology, depicted in Figure 1, for the proposed Reasoning Engine architecture is based on the results of the state-of-the-art analysis and research and the need that arises for extracting information by leveraging rules and axioms from energy efficiency certificates. The next step was the identification of the datasets that could be potentially used for graphical representation. Then, the technical phase initiated with the consumption of the dataset using Confluent Kafka and the persistence and indexing of Neo4j graph storage. NeoSemantics and graph data science plugins of Neo4j enabled the querying of stored data and finally the creation of REST APIs to expose the querying results.

Figure 1. Methodology of the proposed Reasoning Engine architecture.

3.2. Architecture

Figure 2 depicts the proposed architecture of the Reasoning Engine. As shown, the data are produced from the data pre-processing and semantic enrichment layer, where they are homogenized and pre-processed before being sent to the reasoning engine through Kafka topics.

The proposed architecture, Figure 2, consists of five components, namely the Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer, the Neo4j data importers, the Neo4j graph database, the query pre-processing, and the retrieval REST API.

The Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer is a Kafka consumer written in Python 3. It receives data from the data pre-processing and semantic enrichment layer. These are JSON or RDF data that contain EREN energy performance certificates. The consumer receives these data and sends them to the Neo4j data importers (<https://neo4j.com/developer/data-import/> accessed date 29 December 2021). This component is a series of CYPHER scripts that are connected with the Kafka (<https://kafka.apache.org/> accessed date 29 December 2021) consumer through Neo4j Python Driver. The consumed JSON data are channelled to the CYPHER scripts, where they are transformed from JSON data to NEO4J entities (nodes and connections). The Neo4j data importers, as previously mentioned, enable several scripts in order to insert the data into Neo4j structures. After that, these data can be queried, and useful knowledge can derive from them. The Reasoning Engine also provides REST APIs for interacting with the stored metadata in Neo4j. This is the stage where the data are exposed to the upper layer though REST protocols, and it has two sub-components responsible for

the overall functionality. The retrieval REST engine is where external users can submit queries to the Reasoning Engine using POST REST function and JSON payloads. The query pre-processing module receives the JSON data from retrieval REST engine and transforms the JSON data to CYPHER in order to query the Neo4j graph database. The result is the REST API's response, and it is sent back in JSON format. The request presented in Table 1, is an example usage of Reasoning Engine's REST API collection.

Figure 2. Reasoning Engine proposed architecture.

Table 1. Reasoning Engine's REST API collection example.

```
curl -location -request POST 'http://reasoning_engine:5000/leif/service' \
  -header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -data-raw '{
    "heating_total_consumption": ${heating_total_consumption},
    "heating_co2_emission": ${heating_co2_emission},
    "hot_water_total_consumption": ${hot_water_total_consumption},
    "hot_water_co2_emission": ${hot_water_co2_emission},
    "electricity_total_consumption": ${electricity_total_consumption},
    "electricity_co2_emission": ${electricity_co2_emission}
  }
```

Furthermore, the Reasoning Engine component has integrated the neosemantics (<https://neo4j.com/labs/neosemantics/> accessed date 29 December 2021) toolkit, which is used to upload ontologies, RDF data, and other semantic information, and transform them into Neo4j entities. CYPHER language is more flexible than SPARQL, and by leveraging Neo4j plugins such as graph data science, apoc, and neosemantics, the connections between metadata are more transparent.

3.3. Implementation

The implementation of the Reasoning Engine was initiated with the development of a Python Confluent Kafka (<https://docs.confluent.io/platform/current/clients/consumer>.

[html](#) accessed date 29 December 2021) consumer, which was used for receiving JSON and RDF data from the data pre-processing and semantic enrichment layer. The Faust (<https://faust.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> accessed date 29 December 2021) library, which is the Kafka Streams implementation in Python, was used to consume and process events from different time windows and to construct a real time and highly intensive data pipeline.

Before proceeding with more implementation details, it is significant to present the EREN Energy Efficiency Certificates dataset. It consists of of ~300 K rows and 15 columns and contains primary building information, such as registration number, emissions, heating, and cooling demand. Table 2 demonstrates the dataset columns, with a short description for each column and sample values.

Table 2. EREN energy efficiency certificates dataset.

Column	Short Description	Example Value
registration_number	Building's registration number	050190003VI1870TI
registration_date	Building's registration date	1 August 2017
building_usage	Building's primary usage	FAMILY HOUSE
coordinates	Building's location (long, lat)	−4.6788, 40.66
address	Building's address	CALLE DAVID HERRERO 24 05005
municipality	Municipality that the building belongs to	ARENAS DE SAN PEDRO
province	Province that the building belongs to	ABRADA
primary_consumption_ratio	Building's primary consumption ratio (total consumption)	543.0
primary_consumption_rating	Building's primary consumption label	A
co2_emissions_ratio	Building's CO ₂ emissions ratio	61.0
co2_emissions_rating	Building CO ₂ emissions label/rating	E
heating_demand_rating	Building's heating demand rating	E
heating_demand_ratio	Building's heating demand ratio	111.87
cooling_demand_ratio	Building's cooling demand ratio	12.14
cooling_demand_rating	Building's cooling demand rating	C

Figure 3 depicts the data flow in the Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer. More specifically, the EREN data are produced in four different Kafka topics (each topic is related to building data and attributes such as energy certificates, electricity, gas, and diesel consumption). The Faust/Kafka consumer is subscribed to all these topics, and it receives the incoming events. Following, it performs ETL (extract, transform, and load) procedures using the Pandas framework (<https://pandas.pydata.org/> accessed date 20 December 2021), Neo4j Python Driver, and CYPHER GraphQL in order to persist them in the Neo4j graph database.

The CYPHER scripts that persist the consumed events to Neo4j are the reasoning data importers. These scripts receive JSON or RDF data and construct the entities in Neo4j in order to extract hidden patterns and value from buildings metadata. The metadata construction in the graph database aids the intelligent querying and inference over stored data and enhances the machine and deep learning model training. The data from the Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer are channelled to the Reasoning Engine data importers through Neo4j Python Driver. Figure 4 depicts the data flow from the Reasoning Engine consumer through data importers and subsequently to Neo4j.

Figure 3. Data flow in the Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer.

Figure 4. Data flow in the Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer.

The Retrieval REST API, which flow is depicted in Figure 5, is the collection of REST services that expose the stored Neo4j entities on the upper layers of ANALYTICS layer. It was implemented using Flask REST Framework (<https://flask-restful.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> accessed date 23 December 2021), Pandas DataFrames (<https://pandas.pydata.org/pandas-docs/stable/reference/api/pandas.DataFrame.html> accessed date 23 December 2021) and Neo4j Python Driver (<https://neo4j.com/docs/api/python-driver/current/> accessed date

23 December 2021). The services are triggered by HTTP requests that have been submitted. The provided JSON payloads are parsed from the query pre-processing module, which translates the JSON attributes to CYPHER queries.

Figure 5. Data flow in the Reasoning Engine retrieval REST API.

4. Results

In this section, the data flow through the Reasoning Engine’s sub-components are demonstrated. More specifically, the results from the Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer, the data represented in the graph database, and queries using the Reasoning Engine Retrieval REST API will be presented.

4.1. Data Flow in Reasoning Engine Kafka Consumer

The data from the data pre-processing and semantic enrichment module are produced to Apache Kafka in JSON format. The EREN energy certificates, electricity consumption, diesel consumption, and gas consumption data are produced, respectively, to the topics “energy_certificates”, “electricity_consumption”, “diesel_consumption”, and “gas_consumption”. The Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer is subscribed to these four different topics and receives the data using the window functionality of Python Faust library in order to operate batch insert functionalities in the following steps. Figure 6 demonstrates the queued data in the Reasoning Engine consumer.

Figure 6. Data received from Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer.

The goal of this task is to consume events originated from the “energy_certificates” Kafka topic, and these messages are in the format presented in Table 2. Following the events’ consumption, the incoming data are persisted into the Neo4j graph database. The pipeline that stores these data builds the graph entities using CYPHER and semantics plugins of Neo4j, enables the axioms and rules of graph properties, and leverages the metadata connection for the formation of logical inferences.

The Reasoning Engine exposes stored data via the REST services that it exposes. The end user is given the capability of submitting general CYPHER queries to Neo4j. In addition to this general-purpose functionality, prepared queries are also implemented. In this case, the input of the REST APIs is JSON formatted objects which, specifically, include building attributes (e.g., registration number, registration date, primary consumption, address, etc.). Below, some REST APIs are demonstrated. The queries conducted with the Reasoning Engine functionalities can vary; they can either be very simple (e.g., selection of top building certificates) or much more sophisticated queries (e.g., similarity queries or queries that enable graph data science plugin and calculate clusters over the stored graph entities).

4.2. Graph Creation in Neo4j

The Reasoning Engine Kafka consumer enables batch insertion by leveraging the Neo4j Data Importers. Figure 6 depicts the consumption of the incoming events from Reasoning Engine Kafka Consumer and the construction of Neo4j entities for each specific event from Neo4j Data Importers. These importers are a series of CYPHER scripts that receive the batch window data from the Kafka consumer and persist the JSON data to the Neo4j graph database. The embedded JSON objects are now transformed to graph entities. As a result, the data querying will be more effective and significantly faster using graph functionalities. Figure 7 depicts the resulting graph in Neo4j.

Figure 7. EREN data stored in Neo4j.

4.3. Retrieve Data from Reasoning Engine

The data retrieval process from Reasoning Engine is conducted through its REST API. The Reasoning Engine retrieval REST API leverages the Python Neo4j Driver and CYPHER to query the stored EREN data that are structured in graph format. The following REST API call calculates the average primary consumption of buildings classified with primary consumption A.

The response received from the Retrieval REST API, which includes the requested average primary consumption of buildings, is presented in Table 3. The REST API receives

CYPHER queries and, on its backend, transforms the aforementioned query result from Neo4j entities to JSON.

Table 3. Retrieve average primary consumption.

```
curl -location -request POST 'http://reasoning_engine:5000/query' \
  -header 'Content-Type: text/plain' \
  -data-raw 'MATCH
(b:Building)-[:has_primary_cons]->(prim_cons:PrimaryCons)-[:has_primary_label]->(l:Label {rating:
\'"A"\'})
RETURN avg(prim_cons.ratio) as average_primary_cons'
```

The query could be extended in order to find the average primary consumption of buildings located in ABRADA municipality. The new query sent to the Reasoning Engine is demonstrated in Table 4. The following tables (Tables 4 and 5) demonstrate some queries from Reasoning Engine Retrieval REST API.

Table 4. Average consumption for buildings with a primary consumption.

```
[
  {
    "average_primary_cons": 35.88089204257478
  }
]
```

Table 5. Retrieve average primary consumption for buildings located in ABRADA municipality.

```
curl -location -request POST 'http://reasoning_engine:5000/query' \
  -header 'Content-Type: text/plain' \
  -data-raw 'MATCH (b:Building)-[:has_municipality]-(m:Municipality {name: \'"ADRADA (LA)"\'})
MATCH (b)-[:has_primary_cons]->(prim_cons:PrimaryCons)-[:has_primary_label]->(r:Label)
RETURN avg(prim_cons.ratio) as abrada_avg_cons'
```

The response, Table 6, received from the Retrieval REST API is the average consumption requested.

Table 6. Average consumption of building located in ABRADA.

```
[
  {
    "abrada_avg_cons": 349.7089201877938
  }
]
```

5. Conclusions

This paper presented a metadata-driven component that aims to combine existing modern technological breakthroughs in the areas of the machine learning/deep learning and big data in order to develop a new data analytics solution for energy management and energy-efficient buildings. The proposed approach realizes a holistic, state-of-the-art semantics empowered module for the buildings sector.

The prediction of a building's energy consumption is of utter importance since the main goal of today's society is to maintain and protect the natural environment and modernize the urban infrastructure. The architecture that we propose provides the necessary capabilities for boosting scalable big data management and semantics processing, with a vision to reduce some of the major hindrance of previous RDFs (resource description frameworks) and ontologies solutions. This can be achieved by introducing innovative graph databases capable of handling semantic data in a more efficient and meaningful way.

The ideal AI models should be able to predict the energy consumption of the related buildings, and, for that reason, the Reasoning Engine component leverages these building's metadata in order to produce information that can be utilized for the optimization of these AI models. The Reasoning Engine that was introduced will be used to aim at solving problems that may constitute building blocks for more complex problems, such as energy performance prediction, multi-criteria assessment of building interventions, etc.

As future work, the Reasoning Engine graph database will be enriched with further datasets from large-scale pilots in order to combine metadata from different sources and generate more specific and detailed information for different kinds of buildings.

Furthermore, the results of inferences from the Reasoning Engine will be used for data enrichment on a data warehouse system. This system will be based on query engine technologies such as Presto (<https://prestodb.io/> accessed date 26 December 2021), Apache Druid (<https://druid.apache.org/> accessed date 26 December 2021) and Hive (<https://hive.com/> accessed date 26 December 2021) and will aggregate information and queries from multiple sources of data. These data will be enhanced with inference results, and then they could be visualized from a data warehouse system visualization engine that could be implemented in future work with a vision to expand the current architecture. This type of connection could be established by using the microservices-oriented nature of the Reasoning Engine and the fact that it exposes a number of REST APIs. These REST APIs can be integrated with other systems that support the HTTP protocol.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, P.K. and K.A.; methodology, G.K.; software, P.K.; validation, P.K., G.K. and K.A.; formal analysis, P.K.; investigation, K.A.; resources, G.K.; data curation, P.K.; writing—original draft preparation, P.K., G.K. and K.A.; writing—review and editing, P.K., G.K. and K.A.; visualization, P.K.; supervision, D.A.; project administration, D.A. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work has been co-funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the MATRYCS project 'Modular Big Data Applications for Holistic Energy Services in Buildings', grant agreement No 101000158.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The datasets used for Reasoning Engine's implementation can be found in the following url: <https:// analisis.datosabiertos.jcyl.es/explore/dataset/certificados-de-eficiencia-energetica/export/?location=10,41.15005,-2.43043&basemap=jawg.streets>, accessed date 26 December 2021.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

Abbreviations

Definition

AI	Artificial Intelligence
APACHE	APACHE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION
API	Application Programming Interface
BDVC	Big Data Value Chain
CYPHER	Neo4j Graph Database Query Language
DL	Deep Learning
EREN	Regional Energy Agency in Spain
EPC	Energy Performance Certificates
GraphQL	Graphical Query Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IoT	Internet of Things

JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
ML	Machine Learning
ML/DL	Machine Learning/Deep Learning
REST	Representational State Transfer
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SPARQL	Semantic Query Language

References

- Helm, D. The European Framework for Energy and Climate Policies. *Energy Policy* **2014**, *64*, 29–35. [CrossRef]
- Energy Performance of Buildings Directive—European Commission. Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-of-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive> (accessed on 16 December 2021).
- Energy Efficiency Directive—European Commission. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/energy-efficiency/targets-directive-and-rules/energy-efficiency-directive_en (accessed on 16 December 2021).
- Lu, Q.; Parlikad, A.; Woodall, P.; Don Ranasinghe, G.; Xie, X.; Liang, Z.; Konstantinou, E.; Heaton, J.; Schooling, J. Developing A Digital Twin at Building and City Levels: Case Study of West Cambridge Campus. *J. Manag. Eng.* **2020**, *36*, 05020004. [CrossRef]
- Marinakis, V.; Doukas, H. An Advanced Iot-Based System for Intelligent Energy Management in Buildings. *Sensors* **2018**, *18*, 610. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- Marinakis, V.; Doukas, H.; Karakosta, C.; Psarras, J. An Integrated System for Buildings' Energy-Efficient Automation: Application in the Tertiary Sector. *Appl. Energy* **2013**, *101*, 6–14. [CrossRef]
- Marinakis, V.; Karakosta, C.; Doukas, H.; Androulaki, S.; Psarras, J. A Building Automation and Control Tool for Remote and Real Time Monitoring of Energy Consumption. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* **2013**, *6*, 11–15. [CrossRef]
- Marinakis, V. Big Data for Energy Management and Energy-Efficient Buildings. *Energies* **2020**, *13*, 1555. [CrossRef]
- Marinakis, V.; Doukas, H.; Koasidis, K.; Albuflasa, H. From Intelligent Energy Management to Value Economy through a Digital Energy Currency: Bahrain City Case Study. *Sensors* **2020**, *20*, 1456. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
- Marinakis, V.; Doukas, H.; Tsapelas, J.; Mouzakitis, S.; Sicilia, Á.; Madrazo, L.; Sgouridis, S. From Big Data to Smart Energy Services: An Application for Intelligent Energy Management. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.* **2020**, *110*, 572–586. [CrossRef]
- Wei, Y.; Zhang, X.; Shi, Y.; Xia, L.; Pan, S.; Wu, J.; Han, M.; Zhao, X. A Review of Data-Driven Approaches for Prediction and Classification of Building Energy Consumption. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2018**, *82*, 1027–1047. [CrossRef]
- Marinakis, V.; Doukas, H.; Spiliotis, E.; Papastamatiou, I. Decision Support for Intelligent Energy Management in Buildings Using the Thermal Comfort Model. *Int. J. Comput. Intell. Syst.* **2017**, *10*, 882. [CrossRef]
- Papadakos, G.; Marinakis, V.; Konstantas, C.; Doukas, H.; Papadopoulos, A. Managing the Uncertainty of the U-Value Measurement Using an Auxiliary Set along with a Thermal Camera. *Energy Build.* **2021**, *242*, 110984. [CrossRef]
- Ahmad, T.; Chen, H.; Huang, R.; Yabin, G.; Wang, J.; Shair, J.; Azeem Akram, H.; Hassnain Mohsan, S.; Kazim, M. Supervised Based Machine Learning Models for Short, Medium and Long-Term Energy Prediction in Distinct Building Environment. *Energy* **2018**, *158*, 17–32. [CrossRef]
- Sheng, G.; Hou, H.; Jiang, X.; Chen, Y. A Novel Association Rule Mining Method of Big Data for Power Transformers State Parameters based on Probabilistic Graph Model. *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid* **2018**, *9*, 695–702. [CrossRef]
- Miller, J.J. Graph database applications and concepts with Neo4j. In Proceedings of the Southern Association for Information Systems Conference, Atlanta, GA, USA, 23–24 March 2013; Volume 2324.
- Vukotic, A.; Watt, N. *Neo4j in Action*; Manning: Shelter Island, NY, USA, 2015.
- Kunda, D.; Phiri, H. A Comparative Study of NoSQL and Relational Database. *Zamb. ICT J.* **2017**, *1*, 1–4. [CrossRef]
- Angles, R. A Comparison of Current Graph Database Models. In Proceedings of the 2012 IEEE 28th International Conference on Data Engineering Workshops, Arlington, VA, USA, 1–5 April 2012.
- Guia, J.; Gonçalves Soares, V.; Bernardino, J. Graph Databases: Neo4j Analysis. In Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems, Porto, Portugal, 26–29 April 2017.
- Mary Femy, P.F.; Reshma, K.R.; Varghese, S.M. Outcome Analysis Using Neo4j Graph Database. *Int. J. Cybern. Inform.* **2016**, *5*, 229–236.
- Cabra, M. How the ICIJ Used Neo4j to Unravel the Panama Papers. Available online: <https://neo4j.com/blog/icij-neo4j-unravel-panama-papers/> (accessed on 29 October 2021).
- Packer, D. How Walmart Uses Neo4j for Retail Competitive Advantage. Available online: <https://neo4j.com/blog/walmart-neo4j-competitive-advantage/> (accessed on 29 October 2021).
- Allen, D.; Hodler, A.; Hunger, M.; Knobloch, M.; Lyon, W.; Needham, M.; Voigt, H. Understanding trolls with efficient analytics of large graphs in neo4j. *BTW* **2019**. [CrossRef]
- Quamar, A.; Deshpande, A.; Lin, J. NScale: Neighborhood-Centric Analytics on Large Graphs. *Proc. VLDB Endow.* **2014**, *7*, 1673–1676. [CrossRef]
- Jindal, A.; Rawlani, P.; Wu, E.; Madden, S.; Deshpande, A.; Stonebraker, M. Vertexica. *Proc. VLDB Endow.* **2014**, *7*, 1669–1672. [CrossRef]